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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****CLINICAL PROFILE OF PATIENTS WITH ESOPHAGEAL
CANCERS****¹Dr. Muhammad Adnan Bawany, ²Dr. Tufail Ahmed Baloch, ³Dr. Tekchand Maheshwari,
⁴Hamid Nawaz Ali Memon, ⁵Dr. Samar Raza and ⁵Dr. Ali Raza Shaikh**¹Associate Professor Department of Medicine Isra University Hyderabad²Consultant Surgeon & Medical Superintendent Peoples Medical College Hospital³Associate Professor Department of Surgery Isra University Hyderabad⁴Zulekha Hospital Dubai United Arab Emirates⁵Liaquat University Hospital Hyderabad / Jamshoro**Abstract:****OBJECTIVE:** To determine the Clinical profile of patients with esophageal cancers.**PATIENTS AND METHODS:** The one year cross sectional study was conducted at tertiary care hospital. All the patients either gender who were diagnosed as esophageal cancer were included in the study. These patients were allowed to undergo necessary investigations and treatment while the subjects excluded from study were patients who were lost to follow up and the non cooperative patients who not interested to participate in the study while the frequency / percentages (%) and means \pm SD computed for study variables.**RESULTS:** During one year study period total fifty patients with esophageal carcinoma were explored and studied. the frequency for male and female population was 32 (64%) and 18 (36%) with mean \pm sd for age of male and female individuals was 54.47 ± 5.87 and 51.75 ± 7.72 respectively. Gender male 32 (64%) and female 18 (36%), type of lesion exophytic 05 (10%), infiltrative 10 (20%), ulcerative 35 (70%), location upper third 05 (10%), middle third 30 (60%) and lower third 15 (30%). Histological type squamous cell carcinoma 36 (72%) and adenocarcinoma 14 (28%).**CONCLUSION:** It has been found that carcinoma esophagus is the most common gastrointestinal cancer and the most common cause of cancer related death thus early diagnosis offers the only chance of cure in these patients.**KEYWORDS:** Esophagus, Malignancy and Cancer**Corresponding author:***** Dr. Muhammad Adnan Bawany,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Cancer of the esophagus ranks twelfth among the major cancers in the number of new cases diagnosed and seventh in the number of cancer death [1] Its high mortality rate makes it a major concern. Probably no other cancer causes greater misery to the patient due to development of an inability to swallow even fluids [2]. Early stages of the disease are only found serendipitously or during screening of precursor lesion. As a result, the typical patient presents with locally advanced disease with lymph node involvement [3]. Most of the time patients coming to the hospital with advanced disease have a very poor long term prognosis. Esophageal cancers are diagnosed by upper GI endoscopy with multiple biopsies [4]. However C T scan is needed to identify lung and abdominal metastases and also helps in assessing the local respectability of the growth by delineating the invasion into mediastinal structures [5]. CT has poor accuracy for assessment of response to therapy in patients with esophageal cancer. Surgery remains the best option for these patients providing the only chance of cure. Numerous approaches have been described for resection of esophagus, each having its own advantages and disadvantages [6]. Combined modality therapy including radiotherapy and chemotherapy has raised hope for improvement of survival with promising preliminary data [7]. Finally, for palliation of dysphagia in those patients with advanced disease, various newer therapeutic options have been introduced like endoscopic stenting

and laser ablation. Thus this study elaborates a review of current literature pertaining to the disease and concludes by comparing the results of the present study with the former national and international scenario.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The one year cross sectional study was conducted at tertiary care hospital. All the patients either gender who were diagnosed as esophageal cancer were included in the study. These patients were allowed to undergo necessary investigations and treatment while the subjects excluded from study were patients who were lost to follow up and the non cooperative patients who not interested to participate in the study. All the specific patients had thorough clinical history, relevant clinical examination and important investigations to explore the carcinoma esophagus whereas the data was collected on proforma while analyzed in SPSS to manipulate the frequencies, percentages and mean \pm SD.

RESULTS:

During one year study period total fifty patients with esophageal carcinoma were explored and studied. The frequency for male and female population was 32 (64%) and 18 (36%) with mean \pm SD for age of male and female individuals was 54.47 ± 5.87 and 51.75 ± 7.72 respectively. The demographical and clinical profile of study population is presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1: THE DEMOGRAPHICAL AND CLINICAL PROFILE OF STUDY POPULATION

Parameter	Frequency (N=50)	Percentage (%)
AGE (yrs)		
30-39	05	10
40-49	07	14
50-59	15	30
60-69	13	26
70+	10	20
GENDER		
Male	32	64
Female	18	36
TYPE OF LESION		
Exophytic	05	10
Infiltrative	10	20
Ulcerative	35	70
LOCATION		
Upper third	05	10
Middle third	30	60
Lower third	15	30
HISTOLOGICAL TYPE		
Squamous cell carcinoma	36	72
Adenocarcinoma	14	28

DISCUSSION:

Carcinoma esophagus is one of the most common gastrointestinal tract malignancies. It was the second most common gastrointestinal cancer in our hospital second only to carcinoma stomach, constituting 6.2% of all malignancies [8]. According to a study Rao DB, et al [9] the frequency of esophageal cancer was 8.5%. Also, there is very high variability in the incidence of esophageal cancer worldwide. Worldwide, esophageal cancer is much more common in males compared to females. The maximum occurrence of this malignancy in our study was found in the fifth and sixth decade of life which was similar to the nationwide incidence as reported by Napier KJ et al [10]. The overwhelming majority of esophageal malignancies may be classified as either squamous cell carcinomas or adenocarcinomas. Squamous cell carcinomas account for the vast majority of cancers arising in high-incidence areas throughout the world. Seventy two percent of our patients had squamous cell cancer while

twenty eight percent had adenocarcinoma. This reflects the difference in epidemiology and the fact that adenocarcinoma is not rising in incidence in less developed nations like ours compared to the West. In former study approximately 60% of these neoplasms are located in the middle third of the esophagus, whereas 30% and 10% arise in the distal third and proximal third of the intrathoracic esophagus, respectively [11]. In our study, 60% were in middle third, 30% were in lower third and 10% were in upper third esophagus. This closely resembles the former study [11]. Several rare cancers of the esophagus had previously reported as squamous cell carcinoma with sarcomatous features, adenoid cystic and mucoepidermoid carcinomas while none of the patients in this series had any of these types esophageal cancer.

CONCLUSION:

It has been found that carcinoma esophagus is the most common gastrointestinal cancer and the most common

cause of cancer related death thus early diagnosis offers the only chance of cure in these patients.

REFERENCES:

1. Enzinger PC, Mayer RJ. Esophageal cancer. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2003 Dec 4;349(23):2241-52.
2. Oyama T, Tomori A, Hotta K, Morita S, Kominato K, Tanaka M, Miyata Y. Endoscopic submucosal dissection of early esophageal cancer. *Clinical Gastroenterology and Hepatology*. 2005 Jul 1;3(7):S67-70.
3. Yang CS. Research on esophageal cancer in China: a review. *Cancer research*. 1980 Aug 1;40(8 Part 1):2633-44.
4. Kamangar F, Chow WH, Abnet CC, Dawsey SM. Environmental causes of esophageal cancer. *Gastroenterology Clinics of North America*. 2009 Mar 1;38(1):27-57.
5. Shaheen N, Ransohoff DF. Gastroesophageal reflux, Barrett esophagus, and esophageal cancer: scientific review. *JAMA*. 2002 Apr 17;287(15):1972-81.
6. Rizk NP, Ishwaran H, Rice TW, Chen LQ, Schipper PH, Kesler KA, et al. Optimum lymphadenectomy for esophageal cancer. *Annals of surgery*. 2010 Jan 1;251(1):46-50.
7. Gao YT, McLaughlin JK, Blot WJ, Ji BT, Dai Q, Fraumeni JF. Reduced risk of esophageal cancer associated with green tea consumption. *JNCI: Journal of the National Cancer Institute*. 1994 Jun 1;86(11):855-8.
8. Hofstetter W, Swisher SG, Correa AM, Hess K, Putnam JB, Ajani JA, et al. Treatment outcomes of resected esophageal cancer. *Annals of surgery*. 2002 Sep;236(3):376.
9. Rao DB, Desai PB, Ganesh B. Epidemiological Observation On Cancer Of The Esophagus –A Review Of Indian Studies .*Ind J Cancer* 1996;33:55-75.
10. Napier KJ, Scheerer M, Misra S. Esophageal cancer: A Review of epidemiology, pathogenesis, staging workup and treatment modalities. *World J Gastrointest Oncol*. 2014 May 15; 6(5): 112–120.
11. Murphy BM, Xiao L, Patel VR. Pathological complete response in patients with esophageal cancer after the trimodality approach: The association with baseline variables and survival-The University of Texas MD Anderson Cancer Center experience. *Cancer*. 2017 Nov 1;123(21):4106-4113.